

Involvement of Selected Elementary Public-School Teachers in Community Programs in the District of Gapan City

JUNIL A. CONSTANTINO, RACHAEL R. MORALDE, PHD.
NUEVA ECIJA UNIVERSITY
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

PATRICIA MAE G. SESE
HEIDI A. SISON
LEO MARI A. DELA CRUZ
ROSEMARIE V. MIRANDA
VALERIE M. BARENG

Abstract:- This study determined the extent of Involvement of Selected Public-School Teachers in Community Programs in the District of Gapan. The research study was conducted in selected public school in Gapan namely; General Pantaleon Valmonte Elementary School, Balante Elementary School and St. Joseph Elementary School with a total of 50 respondents thirty-six (36) of female and fourteen (14) of male. Descriptive Method was utilized and Google forms was used in conducting the survey. In determining the demographic profile of respondents (age, gender, civil status, length of service, rank and barangay), Frequencies and Percentage was used and rank was added in the involvement of community programs. The researchers used weighted mean and verbal interpretation to measure the data needed. Descriptive interpretation was used to determine the results on each table.

Based on the findings, most of the teachers were elderly and married with a length of service 16-20 years. Most of them are teacher II and teaching in Barangay Pambuan. Major of the participants were involved in Disaster Preparedness and Church and Livelihood Programs.

The respondents were involved in social activities, economic activities and religious activities with a verbal description of “often” and obtained a weighted mean of 2.00 – 2.99.

Takes time for family, add to already heavy loads of the teachers and lack of time for teachers for community programs are the three major problems encountered by the teachers with a verbal description of “agree” and reached a weighted mean of 3.00-3.14. In overall, it shown that the problems that the teachers encountered can be a hindrance on their involvement in community program.

Keywords:- Extent of Involvement, Community Programs, Church Activities and Livelihood, Social Activities, Economic Activities.

I. INTRODUCTION

“The Department of Education is shape up as one of the most effective agents of implementation in government programs because of the number of personnel it handles the strategy place the teacher occupy in the community. The classroom which is under the control of the teacher is a minute version of the whole community. It must be congruent with the community it serves. This statement makes emphasis that making education congruent with the community is one of the multi-furious functions of the teachers. If congruency exist, education would be pleasant and satisfying to the community because it would then be able to solve community problems and meet its needs without much difficulty, thereby making the school an effective agent of transmitting change.

Involvement of the teachers in the activities of the community are one aspect that promotes symbiotic relationship between the school and its environment. The participation of common people in all school programs is highly a determining factor in the progress of school.

The increasing demand of support of public schools from the government through its communities calls for a closer relationship between the school and the community it serves. This means that our school must continuously seek learning situations within the context and realities of community living.

The roles of teachers in community development are great that in every government undertaking program and activity the teachers are always made to play a part, a central part in most cases. This gives reason why teachers involved in different government trust, particularly those directed towards community development. Presidential Decree 6-A, otherwise known as the Educational Development Decree of 1972 gives out the change for this involvement. Section 3 of the said Decree states that among the aims of the Educational System are a) to provide a broad general education that will assist each individual in the specular ecology of his own society to, attain the individual's potential as a human being and enhance the range of quality of individual in group participation in the

basic function of society and b) to respond effectively to changing needs and conditions of the nation through a system educational planning and evaluation. In line with this objective, the school has to plan and program, its activities in such a way to help in the fulfillment of this goals.

A. Statement of the Problem

This study attempts to determine the extent of involvement of selected elementary public-school teachers of Gapan City in community programs. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

- How may the profile of the respondents be described in terms of;
 - Age
 - Sex
 - Civil Status
 - Length of Service
 - Rank
 - Barangay
 - Community Involvement
- How will you describe the extent of involvement of selected elementary public-school teachers of Gapan City in terms of;
 - Social Activities
 - Economic Activities
 - Religious Activities
- What are the problems encounter/confronted by the teachers in the performance of their roles in community programs?

II. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study was to analyzed the extent of involvement that the teachers do. In this regard, the descriptive method of research was utilized. This research method primarily focuses on describing the nature of a demographic segment, without focusing on “why” a particular phenomenon occurs. In other words, it “describes” the subject of the research, without covering “why” it happens. Descriptive research is fact- finding with adequate interpretation. It is something more and beyond just data gathering; the latter is not reflective thinking or research.

Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics and/or behavior of sample population. An important characteristic of descriptive research relates to the fact that while descriptive research can employ a number of variables, only one variable is required to conduct a descriptive study. Three main purposes of descriptive studies can be explained as describing, explaining and validating research findings.

A. The Research Locale

The research study was conducted in public schools in Gapan City, Nueva Ecija namely: Gen. Pantaleon R. Valmonte Elementary School which is one of the biggest public elementary schools in Gapan City, Nueva Ecija while the smallest public elementary school in the District of Gapan includes of Balante Elementary School and St. Joseph Elementary School.

B. Respondent of the Study

This study involved fifty (50) selected classroom teachers drawn from the three (3) representative schools of the district of Gapan. As to how the schools were classified, the researcher considered one (1) big school and two (2) small schools coming from the district identified in terms of population.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents in Different Schools

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents in big school and small schools.

Schools	No. of Classroom Teacher
1. Gen. Pantaleon R. Valmonte Elementary School	28
3. Balante Elementary School	8
4. St. Joseph Elementary School	14
TOTAL	50

Table 1

C. Research Instrument

A questionnaire on the involvement of teachers in community programs were constructed in this study to gather data from the fifty teachers. The questionnaire has three main parts; 1) Involvement in community programs; 2) extent of involvement in community programs, and 3) problem confronting the teachers in community programs.

D. Statistical Techniques Utilized

The following statistical techniques and methods were utilized to interpret and give meaning to data.

a) Ranking

It was utilized in prioritizing the involvement of teachers on community programs. It was further used in describing the role teachers played in the community programs.

b) Weighted Arithmetic Mean

The weighted arithmetic mean is applicable to options of different weights.

Weighted arithmetic mean description on the extent of involvement of teachers in community programs.

Mean	Description
1	Never
2	Often
3	Sometimes
4	Always

Table 2

Weighted mean description on the problems met by the teachers in community development.

Mean	Description
1	SD= Strongly Disagree
2	D= Disagree
3	A= Agree
4	SA= Strongly Agree

Table 3

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The data of the respondents’ demographic profile includes age, sex, civil status, length of service, rank, barangay and community involvement.

Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
23-30	9	18
31-38	14	24
39-46	6	12
47-54	20	40
55 and above	1	2
Total	50	100

Table 4

The table 4 presents the age of the respondents. There was 20 (40%) of respondents are aged 47-54, followed by 14 (28%) aged 31-38, 9 (18%) if the respondents are 23-30 years of age, 6 (12%) belonged to 39-49, and only 1 (2%) is aged 55 and above.

Most active participants at the age 47-54 implies that teacher respondents are still in their productive stage. However, it is also believed that the more one gets older the more one becomes mature and responsible on their roles as a teacher and part of the community.

Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	36	72
Male	14	28
Total	50	100

Table 5

The table 5 shows the sex of the respondents. Female teachers dominated the respondents with 36 or 72%. According to Geetanjali Kalra, the ability to understand students’ mental and emotional needs make women a better choice for teachers in primary schools. They have a better understanding of child psychology that brings a sense of security among children when they step out of their comfort zone. 14 or 28% are male teacher who preferred a better discipline to the students assented by Rajkumar Poddar. Teachers who become involved in the community also come to understand it better, which helps them address the needs of their students more effectively.

Civil Status of the Respondents

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	6	12
Married	44	88
Total	50	100

Table 6

The table 6 shows the civil status of the respondents. It is evident in the table that the married participants had higher frequency and percentage. There was 44 or 88% of the participants were married while the remaining 6 or 12% were single.

Length of Service of the Respondents

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
1 to 5 years	10	20
6 to 10 years	10	20
11 to 15 years	10	20
16 to 20 years	14	28
21 years and above	6	12
Total	50	100

Table 7

The table 7 shows the length of service of the respondents. The data shown that 14 or 28% of the respondents were teaching in 16 to 20 years, 10 or 20% with 11 to 15 years, followed by 10 or 20% with 6 to 10 years, 10 or 20% of participants worked for 1 to 5 years, and 6 or 12% with 21 years and above.

The 28% of the respondents with a length of service 16 to 20 years implies that teachers who teach in a long period of years has widen knowledge and experience of the involvement in community programs.

Rank of the Respondents

Rank	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher I	6	12
Teacher II	18	36
Teacher III	13	26
Master Teacher I	5	10
Master Teacher II	6	12
Head Teacher I	2	4
Head Teacher II	0	0
Total	50	100

Table 8

The table 8 represents the rank of the respondents. It shows that 18 or 36% of participants ranked as teacher II, 13 or 26% were teacher III, followed by 6 or 12% were teacher I and master teacher 2, 5 or 10% were master teacher I, and 2 or 4% were head teacher.

Barangay of the Respondents

Barangay	Frequency	Percentage
Balante, Gapan City	8	16
Pambuan, Gapan City	28	56
Macabaklay, Gapan City	14	28
Total	50	100

Table 9

Table 9 illustrates the barangay of the respondents. From the data shown it is evident that 28 or 56 % of the participant were teachers from Pambuan, followed by teachers in Macabaklay with the frequency and percentage of 14 or 28% and 8 or 16% are teachers from Balante.

Community Involvement of the Respondents

Community Program	Yes		
	f	%	R
1. Disaster Preparedness	44	88	1.5
2. Reforestation/Tree Planting	43	86	3
3. Peace and Order Program	42	84	4
4. Sport Development	31	62	8
5. Population Education	28	56	9.5
6. Applied Nutrition	37	74	6
7. Youth Development Program	35	70	7
8. Church Activities	44	88	1.5
9. Drug Addiction	28	56	9.5
10. Clean and Green Program	38	76	5

Table 10

Table 10 illustrated the community involvement of the respondents. From the data shown, a great number of teachers were involved mostly in four (4) community programs. 44 or 88% of the respondents were involved in Disaster Preparedness Program and Church Activities and Livelihood Program, 43 or 86% were involved in Reforestation/Tree Planting and 42 or 84% in them were involved in Peace and Order Program. Followed by 38 or 76% of the participants were engaged in Clean and Green Program, 37 or 74% associated in Applied Nutrition Program, 35 or 70% of teachers were involved in Youth Development Program, 31 or 62% were engaged in Sport Development Program and 28 or 56% were participated in both Population Education Program and Drug Addiction Program.

B. The Extent of Involvement of Teachers in the Community Programs Picture their Partnership in all Community Endeavors.

The data of the respondents’ teachers Extents of involvement in community programs includes social activities, economic activities and religious activities.

Extent of Involvement of the Respondents

Extent of Involvement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Community Programs			
1. Disaster Preparedness	2.96	Often	4.5
2. Reforestation/Tree Planting	3.00	Sometimes	2.5
3. Peace and Order Program	2.96	Often	4.5
4. Sport Development	2.64	Often	8
5. Population Education	2.66	Often	7
6. Applied Nutrition	3.00	Sometimes	2.5
7. Youth Development Program	2.82	Often	6
8. Church Activities	3.18	Sometimes	1
9. Drug Addiction	2.58	Often	9
10. Clean and Green Program	1.39	Never	10
Overall Weighted Mean	2.72	Often	

Table 11

Table 11 shows the extent of involvement of the respondents. The teacher involved themselves “sometimes” in three community programs, name: Church Activities and Livelihood that obtained a weighted mean of 3.18, ranked as 1 and Reforestation /Tree Planting and Applied Nutrition with a total of 3.00 as weighted mean and ranked as 2.5. “Often” in six community programs name: Disaster Preparedness and Peace and Order Program that obtained a weighted mean of 2.96 ranked as 4.5, Youth Development Program (2.82) ranked as 6, Population Education (2.66) ranked as 7, Sport Development Program (2.64) ranked as 8 and Drug Addiction (2. 58) ranked as 9. Clean and Green Program has weighted mean of 1.39, interpreted as “never” and ranked as 10. In overall, the extent of involvement of the teachers described as “often” and obtained a weighted mean of 2.72.

Social Activities of the Respondents

Social Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
1. Attends birthdays and other activities when invited.	2.54	Often	8
2. Initiates activities for the out-of-school youth.	2.92	Often	4.5
3. Holds meeting for the improvement of the welfare of the community.	2.56	Often	7
4. Directly gets involve in the manifestations of the community outreach program.	2.86	Often	6
5. Lends the school facility to the community affairs and activities.	3.12	Sometimes	1.33
6. Leads community in other relevant activities necessary in improving status like holding TESTDA activities.	2.92	Often	4.5
7. Involves the school and its manpower in health activities like dental and health missions.	3.12	Sometimes	1.33
8. Involves the school classroom and other facilities in times of disaster.	3.12	Sometimes	1.33
Overall Weighted Mean	2.90	Often	

Table 12

The table 12 shows the social activities of the respondents. With regards to social activities, “Lends the school facility to the community affairs and activities, Involves the school and its manpower in health activities like dental and health missions and Involves the school community and other facilities in times of disaster” obtained a weighted mean of 3.12 described as “sometimes”, ranked as 3; followed by “Initiates activities for the out-of-school youth and Leads community in other relevant activities necessary in improving status like holding TESDA activities” attains a weighted mean of 2.92 described as “often” and ranked as 2. In overall, social activities described as “often” and has weighted mean of 2.90. The results implied that teachers are active in their social activities in the community.

Economic Activities of the Respondents

Economic Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
1. Creates and hold meetings for livelihood programs.	2.8	Often	7
2. Creates innovative projects that encourage community residents in improving their way of farming and other occupations.	2.96	Often	4.5
3. Invites people that will lead community residents in improving their lives by means of different livelihood projects.	3.02	Sometimes	3
4. Involves the school facility and teachers in the community activities.	3.08	Sometimes	2
5. Does information dissemination that may help community residents in improving their lives.	2.92	Often	6
6. Participates in the livelihood projects of the community.	3.14	Sometimes	1
7. Gives information and possible disadvantages/effects of the economic projects created by the community.	2.96	Often	4.5
Overall Weighted Mean	2.98	Often	

Table 13

The table 13 shows the economic activities of the respondents. Economic activities rendered that “Participates in the livelihood projects of community” obtained a weighted mean of 3.14, described as “sometimes”, ranked as 1; followed by “Involves the school facility and teachers in the community activities” reached a weighted mean of 3.08 and ranked as 2. In overall, economic activities attained a total of 2.98 weighted mean, described as “often”. The result shown that teachers are involved in economic activities in the community.

Religious Activities of the Respondents

Religious Activities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
1. Holds and uses the school for the mass and other religious activities.	3.24	Sometimes	1.5
2. Organizes religious groups.	2.66	Often	4
3. Participates in the fluvial/other form of parade that honors saints and religious.	2.54	Often	5
4. Participates in the preparation of church and other mass activities.	3.24	Sometimes	1.5
5. Improves rapport with church people and community residents through series of meetings or holding a meeting.	3.06	Sometimes	3
Overall Weighted Mean	2.95	Often	

Table 14

Table 14 shows the religious activities of the respondents. “Holds and uses the school for the mass and other religious activities and Participates in the preparation of church and other mass activities” obtained a weighted mean of 3.24 described as “sometimes”, ranked as 1.5; followed by “Improves rapport with church people and community residents through series of meetings or holding a meeting” attained a weighted mean of 3.06 described as “sometimes” and ranked as 3. It proves that the teacher’s involvement in religious activities brought it in both schools and community. According to Pope Paul VI, 1975 “Modern man listens more willingly to witnesses than to teachers, and if he does listen to teachers, it is because they are witnesses.”

In overall, religious activities obtained a weighted mean 2.95 with verbal description of “often”. The results represented that teachers take part in religious involvement in their community.

C. Problems Confronting Teachers in the Performance of Their Roles in Community Programs

The data of the respondents’ problems met by the teachers in the performance of their roles in community programs.

Problem met by the Respondents			
Problems met by Teacher	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
1.Lack of time for teachers for community program.	3.3	Agree	2.5
2.Adds to the already heavy loads of the teachers.	3.3	Agree	2.5
3.Lack of facilities for community programs.	2.82	Disagree	8.5
4.Indifference of community people towards community programs.	3.00	Agree	5.5
5.Takes time for family.	3.14	Agree	1
6. Lack of cooperation from community residence.	3.00	Agree	5.5
7.No incentives for teachers as recognition for their efficient performance in community programs	2.82	Disagree	7
8.Lack of funding	2.94	Disagree	8.5
9.Lack of insurance of security.	3.02	Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.15	Agree	

Table 15

Table 15 illustrated the problems met by the respondents. Teachers are responsible in the learning of children both academically and humanity in that reason teachers sees that being involved in community programs “add to already heavy loads of the teachers that can result of lack of time and it takes time for family,” these are the three major problems encountered by the teachers .

“Lack of assurance in security” is one of the problems that the teachers considered, nothing can bring joy if you felt safe. The resident in the community is busy in their own life in that case “lack of cooperation from the

community residence” can bring problems in teachers to be involved in community programs. Differences can be a cause of problem and one of them is “Indifference of community people towards community programs”. Mostly these are the hindrances/ problems in the involvement of teachers in community program. With this point of view, the researchers conformed that every person in the community has a thing to say on their involvement in community programs. To convince them, each activity for any program must discussed and explained by a representative of the government agency which initiated the programs.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the research the following conclusion were drawn:

- Among the community activities where in teachers got involved with were Disaster Preparedness, Church Activities and Livelihood, Reforestation/Tree Planting, Peace and Order, Clean and Green Program, Applied Nutrition, Youth Development Program, Sport Development, Population Education and Drug Addiction.

Teacher focused their extent of involvement in Church Activities and Livelihood, Reforestation/ Tree Planting and Applied Nutrition as manifested by their sometimes involvement rating in these programs. In Disaster Preparedness, Peace and Order, Sport Development, Population Education, Drug Addiction and Youth Development Program has often involvement. In the remaining program namely Clean and Green Programs showed never involvement.

- In ten (10) community programs, the teachers performed much in Church Activities and Livelihood. Teachers agreed that they play role very much in this community programs.

In terms of the performance of their role in the community programs, the teachers responded positively in all three (3) activities under the extent of involvement, namely: social activities, economic activities and religious activities regard to the teacher’s performance of their role, they did well in these parts.

- Teachers showed a great evidence to favor themselves in involvement in community programs. They enjoy and more than willing to get involved in community program for self-fulfillment. They sometimes favor their involvement in community programs; specifically Church Activities and Livelihood, Reforestation/ Tree Planting and Applied Nutrition. On the other hand, it was noted that teachers favor their involvement only often in Disaster Preparedness, Peace and Order, Sport Development, Population Education, Drug Addiction and Youth Development Program.
- In majority teachers often agree to that community programs as a good way of bringing the community together and that getting involved in community development is self- fulfilling and encourages self-reliance. They also often agree that teachers are the best agents in community programs and that the community

programs are unnecessary burden to them for they have specific goals to achieve for their pupils and families respectively.

- From the nine (9) problems confronting teachers in the performance of their roles in community programs, they gave special mention to six of those problems. These six (6) are takes time for family, lack of time for teachers for community programs, adds to the already heavy loads of the teachers, lack of insurance of security, indifference of community people towards community programs, lack of cooperation from community residence. The other problems they confronted were no incentives for teachers as recognition for their efficient performance in community programs, lack of facilities for community programs and lack of funding.

B. Recommendations

In the light of the foregoing analysis, the researcher has come up the following recommendations for the teachers to be more effective in their involvement in community programs:

- There should be a continuing harmonious relationship between teachers and the community in the involvement in community programs.
- Activities should be evaluated and assessed before being initiated to ensure the teachers will involve themselves.
- Information drive must be intensified in order for the community people to understand and support the community programs.
- Fund raising projects should be initiated to generate funds for the honorarium of those people who devote their time and efforts for the success of their community programs.
- Resource speakers should be invited to conduct seminars to be attended by the teachers, parents, and community people. This kind of undertaking will help them appreciate the importance and relevance of the different programs formulated in their community.
- The teachers should be more actively involved in activities in their community.

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